

Evaluating Nature-based Solutions for small catchments and streams: Incorporating floods, droughts and biodiversity.

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Introduction

Climate change is increasing extreme fluctuations in both floods and droughts worldwide, resulting also in an increased vulnerability of ecosystems already under pressure from human activities. This creates a need for increasing the climate resilience to better withstand both of these types of hydro-meteorological events using methods that also consider their impact on ecosystems at landscape scale. Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for flooding, water management and droughts are therefore gaining traction as a logical option of choice as they inherently focus on creating benefits for both human use and biodiversity¹.

Upstream catchments used to be dominated by a hydrology in which forests, wetlands, streams, and groundwater play the key roles as natural ecosystem types. However, these catchments

have undergone significant change due to human use in the last century; intensification of agriculture has created a loss in natural ecosystems, urbanisation has increased drainage velocities by paving soils, limiting infiltration towards the groundwater. As a result, infiltration is limited, groundwater is not easily recharged, and rainfall events result in high runoff that not only increase flood risk but also increase soil erosion. This loss of the 'sponge' capacity of the landscape where it can absorb, retain, and slowly drain water is one of the reasons landscapes are vulnerable to increasing frequencies of hydrometeorological events. Figure 1 depicts the increase of water retention in the catchment through the increased use of the surface water, soil and groundwater systems, and how using this 'sponge capacity' leads to reduced flooding and droughts.

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Figure 1 | Schematic showing how the increase in water retained in the surface, soil and ground systems reduces flooding and droughts.

Source: www.spongescapes.eu/policybrief1.

Nature-based Solutions that can help restore this ‘sponge function’ are numerous, including: methods that improve soil conditions in agriculture (e.g. through different cropping, tillage, and irrigation approaches); changes in local land-use to be more in line with the landscape features; and restoration of wetlands, floodplains and streams themselves to give more space to water where it falls. Yet the evidence base related to the performance of these NbS is not yet fully developed, which limits the uptake of these measures. Scientific evidence collected from implemented NbS often focuses only on one aspect of their functioning (e.g. the performance under floods) and lack data on other aspects, such as the response during dry weather spells, the gained biodiversity values, or related response of the hydrological system during droughts.

Despite these challenges, the evidence is slowly growing, and many initiatives are under way to increase this evidence base, both in depth and breadth of application. In this article we show two examples of NbS for small catchments and streams as examples of this progress.

EXAMPLE 1
Assessing catchments for floods and droughts

Drought mitigation measures (DMM) have gained major traction amongst practitioners and water authorities to combat extreme dry conditions due to the significant increase in droughts in central and western Europe over the last few decades². However, the historically wet year of 2023, where Europe experienced around 7% more precipitation than the annual average³, has highlighted the other (extreme wet) side of the coin of climate change impacts. These two opposite extremes highlight the variability between dry and wet extremes, particularly between summer and winter.

Using an integrated ground and surface water modelling approach, we assessed the potential impact of ambitious nature-based DMM such as raising stream beds and blocking drainage channels during winter floods in the Chaamse beken catchment (Netherlands). This catchment lies in the sandy soil region in the south of the Netherlands and the drainage area is 50 km². The catchment is dominated by forested areas (37%) and agricultural land (42%), mainly consisting of pastures, with a considerable urban area (9%) covering the mid to lower catchment. For a future climate scenario (2°C global mean temperature rise by 2050⁴), the assessment included the long-term simulation of groundwater levels as well as the short-term response to different heavy rainfall events. This was achieved by integrating a groundwater/unsaturated zone model (MODFLOW-MetaSWAP) to a hydrodynamic surface water model (Delft3D FM 1D2D)⁵.

The implementation of ambitious drought mitigation measures was shown to be capable of compensating for climate change induced summer groundwater deficits by significantly reducing the drainage of groundwater throughout the catchment, by raising groundwater levels. The reduced drainage is also present during winter, indicated by the reduced baseflow at the downstream outlet, as shown in Figure 2. This also causes significantly raised groundwater levels during the wetter winter months, leading to a reduced floodwater retention capacity in the soils and groundwater during this time. As a result, the peak discharge at the stream outlet increased by 10% during a 1-in-10-year rainfall event, and the flood inundated area doubled in size. Thus, had these ambitious DMM been implemented, it would undoubtedly have led to an even worsened outcome during the 2023 winter floods. The results show that while implementing DMM are beneficial for their primary function (drought mitigation), they can create trade-offs during storm events

Figure 2 | Hydrograph of the streamflow response at the outlet of the Chaamse beken following a 1-in-10-year rainfall event during winter under the reference scenario with implemented drought mitigation measures (DMM, green), and without implemented measures (red).

in shallow groundwater environments. This means that additional flood mitigation measures to improve surface water storage alongside DMM placement need to be considered in the planning process. In this context, it has become increasingly important to begin assessing the implementation of climate adaptation measures more integrally to avoid generating trade-offs. Furthermore, exploring alternative land use schemes that are guided by prevalent environmental conditions need to be developed to build more resilience into catchments to combat drier, wetter, and/or more variable conditions. However, the reduced baseflow that results from the reduced drainage depth of open water bodies, is caused by the removal of drainage ditches and raising of stream beds. Apart from leading to higher flood risk in wet conditions, this increases the risk for aquatic ecology during dry periods. Furthermore, for a scheme to be truly integrative, its evaluation needs to include the effects beyond hydrology such as crop yield, terrestrial biodiversity, and water quality.

EXAMPLE 2

Assessing catchments for flooding considering antecedent conditions

The increase in storm frequency due to climate change will cause flooding to become more likely at times when it would not traditionally occur. Pre-existing wet soil and higher river flowrate conditions are a major driver of this increased likelihood. Using rainfall, hydrometric and photogrammetry data from the Nature based Solutions Wilde Brook test site, in Shropshire, UK, we assessed the effect of wet antecedent soil conditions and higher pre-existing river flowrates on the rainfall-runoff response and water storage provided by the instream wood structures, known as leaky barriers, during low and moderate magnitude storm events (see Figure 3). The monitored NbS test catchment is 5.3 km² with 105 leaky barriers constructed using wood sourced locally along a reach length of 5.36 km, with barrier located every 15-50 m.

Two named storms, Dennis (15th Feb 2020) and Babet (18th October 2023) caused wide-spread national flooding throughout England and Wales (UK), including at the Wilde Brook NbS test catchment. In both storms the water volume was held back by the leaky barriers and released over a period of one to two weeks,

which led to a reduction in the flow velocity as well as attenuation of the storm hydrograph. Dennis was preceded by another storm event, seven days prior, leading to high soil moisture content and elevated pre-existing baseflow conditions. Although the total rainfall occurring during Dennis was 40% lower than during Babet, the wet soil conditions from the storm prior to Dennis led to a significant reduction in water being soaked up by the soil and retained on the surface and an identical amount of effective rainfall entering the river. During storm Dennis this resulted in higher backwater rise upstream of each monitored leaky barrier due to the reduced water storage capacity of the soil and initial higher river flowrate, and greater total water storage utilisation by the barriers along the reach corresponding to around 10,700 m³ which is equivalent to four Olympic size swimming pools, as shown in Figure 4. Consideration of the impact of pre-existing conditions on the flood performance of a protection scheme is crucial and this example illustrates the capability of leaky barriers in providing significant instream surface water storage during a storm where adverse antecedent ground and river level conditions are present.

Moving forward

Working towards climate resilience at the landscape scale will benefit from an approach in which we use the motto 'green where we can and grey where we must'. A wide variety of measures are already available to use as inspiration at the landscape scale⁶, but attention needs to be paid to evaluate their function more fully. For example, Nature based Solutions have not yet been sufficiently tested for moderate and extreme events nor on their interactions between opposite extremes (floods and droughts), so until we have evidence on how they perform during these conditions, we need to be cautious in their design to avoid trade-offs or bad practices, and consider combinations of both flood and drought measures to mitigate potential dis-benefits of a measure for a single purpose. This requires an evaluation for a range of hydro-meteoro-logical events, from high frequency low flow magnitude events to rarer extreme events, as well as considerations of the catch-ment response to the cumulative effect of successive weather events including dry weather spells.

Figure 3 | Quantifying water storage of a leaky barrier (left) at Wilde Brook test catchment (UK) using mobile phone photogrammetry using software Agisoft Metashape (Agisoft LLC). Wireframe mesh in Fusion360 CAD software (right) is generated to enable a relationship between water storage and water height interval to be established. Flow direction is from top to bottom.

Figure 4 | Total net water storage provided by the 105 leaky barriers at the Wilde Brook test reach (UK) for nine storms where the flood return period (t) is $t > 2$ years. Total and effective rainfall volumes are presented which show the effect of dry (orange arrows) and wet (blue arrows) antecedent conditions on the proportion of rainfall that enters the river. Storms Babet and Dennis are comparative storms with identical effective rainfall and wet soil conditions. Effective rainfall is calculated from the river discharge over the storm duration.

Furthermore, investment is needed in monitoring and evaluation of NbS schemes which measure pertinent indicators at appropriate temporal scales (e.g. minutes for flow peaks in small catchments, days/weeks for water storage and soil moisture content, weeks/months for groundwater level).

Performance indicators should not be limited to one metric (e.g. changes in peak flow) and consideration should instead be given to several metrics, such as river level, groundwater level, water storage volume, soil moisture, stream velocity, and peak flow lag time, and be reported in the context of the catchment scale and event magnitude.

In addition, there is also a need to evaluate the impact of measures in terms of their role in providing other ecosystem services and biodiversity benefits. The selection of which measure is appropriate in a given situation is determined not only by the local biophysical situation, but also by the social context and the creation of overarching strategies together with the stakeholders of the region. This calls for a close link with social and socio-economic experts to help make the transition to climate resilient landscapes. The IAHR Science community can be part of this transition by bringing valuable insights in the system functioning and building a multi-faceted evidence base to help stakeholders choose and decide based on objective information.

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